

RESULTS AND EXPLOITATION OF THE PROJECT PARE: PERSPECTIVES FOR AERONAUTICAL RESEARCH IN EUROPE

L. M. B. C. Campos ⁽¹⁾, J. M. G. S. Oliveira ⁽²⁾, P. G. T. A. Serrão ⁽³⁾

⁽¹⁾ CCTAE, IDMEC, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, Av. Rovisco Pais 1, 1049-001 Lisboa, Portugal, Email: luis.campos@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

⁽²⁾ CCTAE, IDMEC, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, Av. Rovisco Pais 1, 1049-001 Lisboa, Portugal, Email: joliveira@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

⁽³⁾ CCTAE, IDMEC, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, Av. Rovisco Pais 1, 1049-001 Lisboa, Portugal, Email: pedro.a.serrao@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

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ABSTRACT:

The main aim of the project PARE (Perspectives for Aeronautical Research in Europe) is to assess the progress made towards achieving the 23 ACARE goals in the Flightpath 2050 document and to propose relevant measures as a set of recommendations based on an extensive report. One of the 15 chapters of the report concerns emerging technologies addressed in the present paper: electrification, additive manufacturing, efficient production 4.0, telecommunications, cybersecurity, big data, artificial intelligence, new materials, nanotechnologies and nanotube structures.

1. INTRODUCTION

The guiding objectives for the aeronautics research program of the European Union have been established by ACARE (Advisory Council for Aeronautical Research in Europe) in a number of documents, most notably the 23 ACARE goals in Flightpath 2050. The main aim of the project PARE (Perspectives for Aeronautical Research in Europe) is to assess the progress made so far towards those goals and suggest measures to close the remaining gap. This assessment forms the first part consisting of chapters 2 to 6 of the PARE yearly report, publicly available at [1]

The second part of the report addresses major topics: (chapter 7) long-range air transport; (chapter 8) emerging technologies; (chapter 9) cooperation beyond Europe's borders; (chapter 10) attracting young talent; (chapter 11) increasing the participation of women. The second part of the report has led to the formulation of a set of 35 PARE objectives whose implementation supports the achievement of the 23 ACARE goals. The 23 ACARE goals and 35 PARE objectives have been collected in a set of 58 recommendations for aeronautics research in Horizon Europe available

as Chapter 1 of the PARE report and as a brochure.

The third part of the PARE report consists also of 5 chapters, two of which are "what if" studies, presented as posters, on the Boeing MMA Aircraft (chapter 13) and prospects for the Chinese aircraft industry (chapter 12). The chapter 14 is a case study on the Boeing B737Max accidents, and the chapter 15 on propulsion technologies and chapter 16 on environmentally friendly aviation are the subject of papers presented in this PARE session. This oral presentation is a brief introduction to the PARE project and session, and goes on to focus on chapter 9, on emerging technologies.

2. EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES

The PARE yearly report is a rather comprehensive document covering most aspects of aviation, and the PARE session at AEC 2020 selects a few of the most technology oriented chapters. Even a single chapter 9, on emerging technologies, is more than can be presented in detail in a single presentation. Among the emerging technologies relevant to aviation, including those arising from other sectors, ten are mentioned:

- electrification
- additive manufacturing
- efficient production 4.0
- telecommunications
- G5
- cybersecurity
- big data
- artificial intelligence
- new materials
- nanotube structures

Each of these topics could support a presentation or session by itself, and thus a very brief account is given here, with just three elements for each

- what is the long-term promise?
- how far have we reached?
- what are the main remaining challenges?

The following are just a few highlights.

3. ELECTRIFICATION

Electrification in aviation is mentioned mainly in 3 contexts: (i) electric or hybrid propulsion; (ii) more electric aircraft with replacement of other systems; (iii) electric towing and taxiing to reduce emissions at airports. Concerning electrical propulsion can be considered (a) solar power, (b) battery power and (c) hybrid propulsion.

3.1. Solar Powered Aircraft

- Promise: Long/infinite endurance as a sensor/relay platform operating as an alternative to satellites much closer to earth.
- Achievements: round the world flight with many stops including a pilot.
- Challenges: large wing area to collect modest solar energy, operation above clouds, battery weight to fly at night, time to climb, vulnerability to weather, light structure and small payload.

3.2. Battery Powered Aircraft

- Promise: Low/no emissions low-cost transport like urban V/STOL.
- Achievements: small drones, light planes.
- Challenges: low energy density of current batteries; low power-to-weight and power-to-volume ratio; range limited to about 500 km with current battery technology; improvements dependent on new solid-state batteries with better energy density but challenging on cost and large scale production.

3.3. Hybrid Regional Aircraft

- Promise: lower emissions and costs up to 1000 km range.
- Achievements: demonstrator programs being pursued.
- Challenges: using cruise optimized efficient engines backed by electric/battery power for other stages of flight; having enough electric power reserve for climb, airport diversion; integration issues.

3.4. Long-range aircraft

- Promise: turbine engine drives alternator that supplies electric energy to efficient distributed propulsion.
- Achievements: high-power generators and electric motors with high-efficiency (>93%) driving propellers.
- Challenges: tens of MW of power imply thousands of volt and ampere; high voltage can lead to sparks and electromagnetic interference; large currents imply energy losses and dissipation; "superconducting cables" require cryogenic temperatures if they provide a viable energy transport; the alternative is distributed integrated power-propulsion units.

4. ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING

- Promise: Local manufacture of spare parts with no need for stocks or awaiting deliveries.
- Achievements: manufacture of complex pieces in a slow process with quality constraints.
- Challenges: moving from small scale slow production to fast large scale production; quality issues depending on number of layers; limited choice of base materials: quality, repeatability and certification; access to all design information needed.

5. EFFICIENT PRODUCTION 4.0

- Promise: Approach/match the productivity of high-rate production chains using just-in-time and other efficiency enhancements.
- Achievements: works in the automotive and other industries.
- Challenges: adaptation to lower production rates of aviation, with greater complexity and higher quality standards; large investment in facilities, machinery, software and training; transition from and compatibility with traditional production methods.

6. TELECOMMUNICATIONS

- Promise: larger data rates through increased bandwidth without signal degradation, loss, interference, or interruption.
- Achievements: impressive progress moving to higher frequencies with benefits (more bandwidth, smaller antennas).
- Challenges: signal generation, propagation and processing, minimizing interference, degradation, interruption or loss of signal; cyber and intrusion issue.

7. G5

- Promise: it is going to be widely available with high data rates so why not use it in aviation?
- Achievements: could it be part of the solution for air traffic management (ATM) of drones and urban air transport.
- Challenges: there are stringent requirements for safe ATM on quality and continuity of signal, no interruption, saturation or interference from other services.

8. CYBERSECURITY

- Promise: secure, hacker-resistant data files, communications and systems.
- Achievements: easier to list spectacular failures. Needs parallel monitoring, early detection of anomalies, isolation of affected parts, reassignment of compromised functions to units operating correctly, elimination of intrusions, requalification of affected parts; much better if cyber resistance is designed-in from the outset.
- Challenges: there is no 100% protection of

software by software; encryption cannot be decoded if used only once; protection of systems at many levels: design, production, operations, communications, marketing, subcontracting all of which can be paths for intrusion.

9. BIG DATA

- Promise: to make good use of vast amounts of available data.
- Achievements: improvements in fault prediction, detection and isolation, predictive maintenance, incorporation of operational experience in procedures and design.
- Challenges: processing large amounts of data in an efficient way, finding the relevant pieces of data in a large set, interpreting and exploiting the results reliably.

10. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

- Promise: perform tasks much faster than humans, without errors, in complex environments.
- Achievements: fast, error-free execution of tasks based on extensive training with high-quality data sets covering all possible occurrences in a given scenario.
- Challenges: artificial intelligence has no imagination and cannot deal with situations it has not been trained for; quality of results depends on abundance of quality training material; training material must cover extensively every possible occurrence; large investment in data collection and validation, needs large number of realistic simulations, requires reliable independent validation.

11. NEW MATERIALS, NANOTECHNOLOGIES AND NANOSTRUCTURES

- Promise: contributions to the efficiency of large 'big bird' aircraft, eventually making possible small 'insect size' drones.
- Achievements: very diverse: composite, ceramic materials and alloys, fluidic control, micromechanical devices, etc.
- Challenges: many specific to the technology. Example: nanotube structures: could have the same strength with a fraction of the weight by being mostly hollow with a nanotube lattice. The nanotubes tend to coalesce rather than organize a lattice, even in laboratory conditions. Transition to production another challenge.

12. CONCLUSION

The PAREproject takes the 23 ACARE Flightpath 2050 as a starting point to

- Assess progress towards achieving those goals and recommend actions to close the remaining gap.

- Those actions are grouped in 35 PARE objectives whose implementation supports the achievement of the ACARE goals.
- The ensemble of 58 recommendations (concerning 23 ACARE goals and 35 PARE objectives) for aeronautics research in Horizon Europe is available as a brochure [2].
- The background information supporting in detail the 58 recommendations is contained in the PARE yearly report available on-line [1].
- This paper concerns mostly an overview with some highlights on chapter 9 – Emerging Technologies.
- Two other oral presentations will address chapter 15 – Propulsion Technology and chapter 4 – Environmentally Friendly aviation.
- Two posters will address what if studies: chapter 12 – The Boeing MMA aircraft and chapter 13 – The Chinese aircraft industry.
- This provides a sample of the PARE project that covers most aspect of aviation in its 3 yearly reports.

13. REFERENCES

1. PARE project (2019). Second Yearly Report - Perspectives for Aeronautical Research in Europe 2019 Report. Available on-line at <https://www.pareproject.eu/publications>
2. PARE project (2019). 58 PARE Recommendations for Aeronautical Research in Horizon Europe. Available on-line at <https://www.pareproject.eu/copy-of-about-pare>